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Abstract

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most common cause of dementia and behavioral alteration. Among multiple aspects of AD, altered sleep pattern or circadian rhythm is the lastly reported concern. Edible and medicinal mushrooms could ameliorate both sleep disturbances or circadian rhythm and AD manifestations. Based on the available information, the trio "Circadian rhythm-AD-Mushroom" has been related. Information provided in this article sheds light on therapeutic possibility of mushrooms against sleep disorder and AD.

Keywords: Alzheimer's disease; circadian rhythm; learning and memory; mushroom; sleep disorder.

Disrupted Circadian rhythm (CR) in Alzheimer's disease (AD)

Alzheimer's disease (AD), named after its discoverer Alois Alzheimer, is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized by loss of memory and behavioral alteration [1]. Abnormal accumulation of amyloid beta (A β) and neurofibrillary tangles (NFT) in the neurons cause AD. AD is an age-onset disease whose manifestations occur mostly after age 65 [2]. However, progression of AD occurs since early 40ths [3]. Numerous causes have been linked with AD onset and progression [4]. Among them genetic, environmental, behavioral and life-style related issues are most crucial. Recently, a novel factor,

"abnormal sleep pattern" or "disturbed circadian rhythm" has been associated with AD pathogenesis [5]. "Circadian rhythm" is a biological system of normal "sleep and wake cycle". It is maintained by genic expression and dysregulated expression of the gene "PERIOD (PER)" causes alteration in "sleep and wake cycle" [6]. More than 45% of the AD subjects suffer from disturbances in circadian rhythm [7]. Altered sleep pattern becomes manifested long before memory and learning related abnormalities of the AD patients [8]. Thus, altered sleep pattern could be considered as an early sign of AD and management strategy aimed at maintaining normal sleep-wake-pattern could help alleviating AD symptoms.

Hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis and mushrooms

The neuroendocrine system "hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis" maintains stress response of the body through

releasing hormones such as cortisol [9-13]. Mushrooms mediate state-of-relaxation and sleep through modulating the hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis. *Ganoderma lucidum* had been reported to enhance non-REM sleep pattern [9-13].

Effect of mushrooms on GABAergic system

Gamma amino butyric acid (GABA) an inhibitory neurotransmitter that aids in smoothening and calming the nervous system [14]. *Ganoderma lucidum* contains a plethora of bio-

components of which some are tri-terpenoids in nature [15]. Among the functional groups of the tri-terpenoids, some mimic the structure of GABA [16].

These tri-terpenoids act as GABA agonists and can directly aid in relaxation and restfulness [15-16]. Also, some of the tri-

terpenoids enhance the production of GABA strengthens GABA activity [15-16].

Effect of mushrooms on cortisol levels

Cortisol is a steroidal hormone that is involved in sleep-wake cycle [18]. Its level rises in the morning. In other words, during awakened state, cortisol level remains high or vice versa [18]. Mushroom ingredients lower the levels of cortisol hormones and provokes the state of relaxation and sleepiness [10-12, 19].

Buffering effect of mushrooms on blood sugar levels

Mushrooms aid in amelioration of diabetes mellitus and diabetes insipidus [20]. Excessive high or low level of blood glucose is an alarming state that leads to AD, stroke and other neurological and muscular derangements [10]. Hypoglycemia at sleep could cause arousal and disturbed sleep pattern. Mushrooms aid in keeping blood glucose level normal and overcome the unusual wake up problem.

Effect of mushrooms on pineal gland

The pineal gland in the brain produces the hormone melatonin (N-acetyl 5-methoxytryptamine) that is regulated by the circadian rhythms. Melatonin is intricately linked with the pathogenesis of AD. Normally, melatonin level peaks at midnight and its level lowers with aging [21]. Besides, suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN) disruption causes reduced melatonin production and disrupted circadian rhythm as well as increased AD pathogenesis [21-23]. Compared with the normal subjects, AD patients show reduced level of melatonin and increased oxidative stress pattern. Melatonin could reduce AD pathogenesis through lowered amyloid beta pathogenesis [21-23]. Signaling effect of pineal gland is modulated by mushrooms in such a way that deeper sleep pattern is ensured [21-23]. Shifting the pineal gland's response to "night/darkness" than to the "daylight/extreme light", mushrooms provoke a state of deeper sleep [21-23].

Effect of mushrooms on parasympathetic nervous system

A sound sleep requires shifting from "fight or flight state" to

"rest and digest state". Parasympathetic nervous system regulates this shifting pattern. Mushrooms' effect on the parasympathetic nervous system alters the "fight or flight state" to "rest and digest state" that facilitates rest and sleep [10-12].

Anti-oxidative and anti-inflammatory effects of mushrooms

Anti-oxidative and anti-inflammatory effects of mushrooms act as alternative to the inflammatory response of the nervous and bypasses the immunologic "cytokine storm" generation [24-27].

Serotonin enhancement effect of mushrooms

Serotonin (5-hydroxytryptamine, or 5-HT) is a mood stabilizer that acts as both neurotransmitter and hormone [28]. Loss of serotonin has been associated with AD pathogenesis [29]. Mushrooms enhance the level of serotonin and maintains a state of euphoria [30-31].

Modulation of gut microbiota by mushrooms

Mushrooms provide support to the growing of gut microbiota that acting through the vagus nerve, maintains a state of restfulness [32].

Blood pressure lowering effect of mushrooms

High blood pressure is associated with multiple pathophysiological states including sleep disturbances and AD [34]. Mushrooms lower blood pressure and aids in maintaining steady sleep pattern [35-36].

Conclusion

Both edible and medicinal mushrooms are potent in ameliorating disrupted circadian rhythm and AD pathophysiology. Though detailed mechanism is not elucidated yet, future research entailing mushrooms would aid in withstanding AD and circadian rhythm pathophysiology.

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